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SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF VOICE WHICH IS THE CATEGORY OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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***Annotation:** In linguistics, the term "voice" refers to a grammatical category of verbs that indicates the relationship between the subject and the action expressed by the verb. There are typically two primary voices in many languages: active and passive. Understanding and utilizing voice in language helps convey information about the relationships between the entities involved in an action and can also affect the overall tone and emphasis of a sentence.*

***Key words:** Verb, voice, active, passive, reflexive, superlative, togetherness.*

***Аннотация:** В лингвистике термин "залог" относится к грамматической категории глагола, которая указывает на связь между подлежащим и действием, выражаемым глаголом. Во многих языках обычно существует два основных залога: активный и пассивный. Понимание и использование голоса в речи помогает передать информацию об отношениях между субъектами, участвующими в действии, а также может повлиять на общий тон и акцент предложения.*

***Ключевые слова:** глагол, залог, активный, пассивный, рефлексивный, превосходная степень, единение.*

***Annotatsiya:** Tilshunoslikda "nisbat" atamasi fe'lning grammatik toifasiga ishora qiladi, bu mavzu va fe'l bilan ifodalangan harakat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni ko'rsatadi. Ko'pgina tillarda odatda ikkita asosiy nisbat mavjud: aniq va majhul. Nutqda nisbatni tushunish va undan foydalanish harakat va holatda ishtirok etayotgan egalar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar haqidagi ma'lumotlarni etkazishga yordam beradi, shuningdek, gapning umumiy ohangi va urg'usiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Fe'l, nisbat, aniq, majhul, o'zlik, ortirma, birgalik.*

Grammar is essential for effective communication in English, as it establishes the framework and guidelines for coherent expression. By studying grammar, individuals can improve their writing and verbal abilities while gaining a better grasp of the language. However, learners may encounter challenges when attempting to compare their native language with a foreign one, such as English. This article will explore the comparison of voice, a grammatical aspect of verbs, in both English and Uzbek languages.

We are referring to various grammatical forms used to show the connection between a transitive verb and its subject and object when we mention the concept of voice. Most English grammar experts generally identify just two voices in English: the active voice and the passive voice. [2;29]. In Uzbek language, voice refers to the extent to which the doer is involved in the action or state denoted by the verb form. This involvement is indicated by verb forms that show the relationship between the subject and the action or state, and this system of verb forms is known as the voice category. According to the function of relative adverbs, lexical form-forming adverbs are considered. Relative forms of the verb added after the base part. The verb has 5 voices forms: 1. Aniq nisbat (probably as: Active voice). 2. O'zlik nisbat (probably as: Reflexive voice). 3. Majhul nisbat (probably as: Passive voice). 4. Orttirma nisbat (probably as: Causative voice). 5. Birgalik nisbat (probably as: Togetherness voice). [1;240]

... but I will *write* to your mother. [3;254]

... Besh kun kecha-yu kunduz uxlamay, ushbu xotirani *yozdin*. ... [4;42]

In grammar, the active voice is the most common and basic voice, where the subject performs the action expressed by the verb. In languages like Uzbek, the active voice is typically formed by using a zero morpheme, which means that the verb form itself indicates that the subject is carrying out the action. [2;30]

This is the proof for Uzbek language: In the active voice, the subject performing the action or state is indicated by the verb form. [1;240] As it is possible to see from the examples above in both English and Uzbek languages verbs *write* and *yozdin* were used in active voice (aniq nisbat) with zero morphemes.

... In spidery writing *was written* a date of some sixteen years previously, and below that ... [3;779]

... Shuni yaxshi bilamanki, 1954-yilning o'rtalarida Saidaxondan hamma ayblar *olib tashlandi* ... [4;223]

The passive voice is created by the covert morpheme (be-ed). [2;30] In Uzbek language, the passive voice is formed morphologically by adding the suffix -(i)n, -(i)l [1;241]. The majority of linguists acknowledge the concept of voice in modern English, with some recognizing two voices: active and passive and others arguing for three

voices. In addition to the active and passive voices, some scholars include the reflexive voice, which uses self pronouns in a semantically weakened form, as seen in the following sentence [2;29].

... Don't worry, I'll behave *myself* ... [3;355].

It is hard to disagree with the criticisms of these theories, as they lack compelling evidence [2;29].

Conversely, in Uzbek language, the reflexive voice denotes an action or situation that the performer does on their own. It is constructed with the affixes -n(in), -l(il) [1;241].

... U ketgandan keyin shoshilib *kiyindim-u* ... [4;223]

The construction of active, passive, and reflexive voices appears similar in both English and Uzbek languages. However, there are distinct differences between the two languages. There are not superlative voice and togetherness voice in English but in Uzbek language there are. The superlative voice represents an action or situation carried out by another person or thing under an influence. [1;243]

This is formed by these affixes: *-t, -dir, -tir, -giz, qiz, -kiz, -g'iz, -kaz, gaz, -ir, -ar, -iz.* [1;243]

... Bir kuni maktab direktori uni dars paytida idoraga *chaqirtirdi* ... [4;15]

Togetherness voice refers to a verb form that shows an action or state carried out by multiple individuals together. This form is created using the suffixes *-sh* and *-ish*. [1;244].

... Unga «Hoji ona» deb janoza *o'qishdi* [4;103].

To sum up, it is important to note that English and Uzbek languages have distinct grammatical structures; English is analytical while Uzbek is synthetic. Despite this difference, similarities can still be observed in the morphological structure of the voice in the examples provided.

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